

Studies in the synthesis of Furocoumarins. Part XXI : Synthesis of Furocoumestan derivatives

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7-Allyloxy-4-hydroxycoumarin, on dehydrogenative coupling with catechol in the presence of potassium iodate gave 7-allyloxy-11, 12-dihydroxy coumestan ; which on methylation followed by Claisen migration, cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid and dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished 5'-methyl-11,12-dimethoxy furo (2,3-h) coumestan. 5',8-Dimethyl-11,12-dimethoxy furo (3,2-g) coumestan was similarly synthesised from 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin.

COUMESTAN and Furocoumestan derivatives, such as coumestrol¹, Erosnin² etc. have assumed importance in recent years. They occur in nature and also possess estrogenic properties. It was, therefore, thought of interest to study some reaction of hydroxy coumestan derivatives and to build up furan ring on it and to study the structure activity relationship of the furocoumestan derivatives. We report here the synthesis of 5'-methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy furo (2,3-h) coumestan (IV) and 5',8-dimethyl-11, 12-dimethoxy furo (3,2-g) coumestan (V).

7-Allyloxy-4-hydroxycoumarin³ (I) prepared by the condensation of 4-allyloxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone with diethyl carbonate in the presence of sodium metal according to Boyd and Robertson⁴, on dehydrogenative coupling with catechol in the presence of potassium iodate⁵, gave 7-allyloxy-11, 12-dihydroxy coumestan (IIa). This on methylation with dimethyl sulphate, gave 7-allyloxy-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (IIb). (IIb), on Claisen migration in an atmosphere of nitrogen in refluxing dimethylaniline, afforded 7-hydroxy-8-allyl-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (IIc). This on trituration with conc. sulphuric acid, gave 5'-methyl-11,12-dimethoxy-4', 5'-dihydrofuro (2,3-h) coumestan (III), which underwent dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal to give 5'-methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy-furo (2,3-h) coumestan (IV).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin³, on dehydrogenative coupling with catechol, gave 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-11, 12-dihydroxy coumestan (IId). This, on methylation and Claisen migration afforded 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methyl-11,12-dimethoxy coumestan (IIe). (IIe) on cyclisation with con. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished 5',8-dimethyl-11, 12-dimethoxy furo (3,2-g) coumestan (V).

(a) $R = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$

(b) $R = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = CH_3$,
 $R_2 = R_3 = H$

(c) $R = R_3 = H$; $R_2 = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$;
 $R_1 = CH_3$

- (d) $R = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = R_3 = H$;
 $R_2 = CH_3$
- (e) $R = H$; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$;
 $R_3 = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$
- (f) $R = -CH_2 - CH = CH_2$; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$;
 $R_3 = H$

Experimental

U/V Spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-2 model and i.r. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 457 model.

7-Allyloxy-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (Iib): 4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy coumarin³ (1 g.), catechol (0.5 g.), and sodium acetate (2 g.) was dissolved in acetone (25 ml.). The solution prepared by potassium iodate (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) in 10 ml. water was added to above solution dropwise with constant stirring allowed it to stand for 1 hr. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate. Yield 0.8 g. m.p. $>300^\circ$ and it was insoluble in common organic solvents. It was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate and developed green colouration with ferric chloride solution. The product (2 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.6 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on water bath for 8 hr. After the evaporation of acetone, the residue was decomposed with water. The product was filtered and washed with dil. sodium hydroxide, dried and crystallised from acetic acid m. p. 198° . Yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 68.47; H, 4.81%. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 68.19; H, 4.54%.) IR Spectra (Nujol): 1733 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group), 1275 cm^{-1} (Aromatic ether linkage)

7-Hydroxy-8-allyl-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan: (Iic) 7-Allyloxy-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (2 g.) was refluxed in dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) in the presence of nitrogen atmosphere for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated product was filtered and the residue was treated with dil. sodium hydroxide solution and filtered. The filtrate was acidified and the product crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 258° . Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 67.70; H, 4.44%. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 68.19; H, 4.54%.) IR spectra: 1690 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $C=O$ group)

5'-Methyl-11,12-dimethoxy-4',5'-dihydro furo(2,3-h) coumestan: (III) 7-Hydroxy-8-allyl-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (0.7 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (4 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and water. The product was filtered, washed with dil. sodium hydroxide, dried and crystallised from the mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether, m. p. 203° . Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 67.72; H, 4.72%. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 68.19; H, 4.54%.)

5'-Methyl-11,12-dimethoxy furo(2,3 h) coumestan: (IV) 5'-Methyl-11,12-dimethoxy-4', 5'-dihydro furo (2,3-h) coumestan (0.8 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.6 g.; 10%), in diphenyl ether (6 ml.) for 20 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and after cooling light petroleum was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed several times with light petroleum. It crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m. p. 253° . Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 68.28; H, 3.93%. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 68.57; H, 4.00%.) IR Spectra (Nujol) 1740 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group) λ_{Max}^{MeOH} , 242 and 340 nm. ($\log \epsilon$ 4.57 & 4.40)

5',8-Dimethyl-11,12-dimethoxy furo(3,2-g) coumestan: (IIf) 4-Hydroxy-7-allyloxy-8-methyl coumarin (1 g.)³, catechol (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (2 g.) was dissolved in acetone (25 ml.). The solution prepared by potassium iodate (0.5 g.) and sodium acetate (1 g.) in 10 ml. water was added to above solution dropwise with constant stirring and allowed it to stand for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was worked up as before, m. p. $>300^\circ$. Yield 0.5 g. The product was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate and developed green colouration with ferric chloride solution. The product (2 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.6 g.), potassium carbonate (4 g.), acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on water bath for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The product crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 212° . Yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 68.42; H, 4.14%. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.91%)

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan: (IIf) 7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy coumestan (2 g.) was refluxed in dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) in the presence of nitrogen atmosphere for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The product crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 247° . Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 69.07; H, 5.6%. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.92%)

5'-Methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy-8-methyl-4', 5'-dihydro furo (3,2g) coumestan: 7 Hydroxy 6 allyl 8 methyl 11, 12 dimethoxy coumestan (0.8 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (4 ml.) for 10 min. The reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and water. The product was filtered, washed with dil. sodium hydroxide, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 265° . Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 68.55; H, 4.60%. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.85; H, 4.91%)

5'-Methyl-11,12-dimethoxy-8-methyl furo (3,2-g) coumestan: (V) 5'-Methyl-11, 12-dimethoxy-8-methyl-4', 5'-dihydro furo (3,2 g) coumestan (0.8 g.) was refluxed with palladised charcoal (0.6 g.; 10%) in diphenyl ether (6 ml.) for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The compound crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 288° . Yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 69.31; H, 4.15%. $C_{21}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 69.23; H, 4.39%) IR Spectra (Nujol) 1720 cm^{-1} (lactonyl $>C=O$ group). λ_{Max}^{MeOH} , 286 and 350 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.81 and 4.27).

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